

**THE NEED TO EDUCATE STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF GENDER
EQUALITY**

Rajabova Zamira Ravshanbekovna .

Urganch State University

"Pedagogy and psychology"

student of the 3rd level of education

Annotation. This article analyzes the introduction of the concept of gender into science, gender equality, gender issues in social life in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the political and social situation of gender equality relations. Also, the specific aspects of the implementation of the gender approach to the higher education system, the creation of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in higher education are interpreted from a scientific point of view.

Key words: gender approach, right, opportunity, higher education, student, upbringing, advisory board, effective mechanism.

Sign in . The idea of gender equality was fully formed in the last decades of the 20th century, it was understood that it is a socio-cultural process that changes on the basis of different spiritual and moral requirements in different eras and socio-cultural conditions. One of the most important pedagogical conclusions in the formation of gender culture is the role of the family, school, peers, mass media (radio, television, internet) in educating young people in the spirit of gender equality. The policy of the United Nations Organization (UN) aimed at ensuring human rights and freedoms is aimed at alleviating these social differences, creating equal opportunities for them in all areas of economic and social development, and forming the idea of gender equality. The educational system is a mirror that reflects the society as a whole, it has its influence on it, and in turn, the changes in education do not affect the development of the society. Therefore, the educational system should be the initiator of changes in the introduction of gender equality in society. This, in turn, requires the development of theoretical-methodological bases for the implementation and management of the gender approach to the higher education system. Because the stable progress and development of every country depends on the human factor, especially the scientific, creative and spiritual potential of the young generation. As noted, achieving gender equality today is not only one of the democratic values, but also an important factor of socio-economic and spiritual development. The experience gained on a global scale shows that it is precisely in countries where there are equal opportunities for men and women that the population's well-being and social-political activity are at a high level, and the

success of reforms is ensured. "Gender" is a social aspect of the relationship between women and men that is manifested in all spheres of society's life and activity, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education and science [1]. The most important importance of educating young people in the spirit of gender equality is that they, first of all, help girls to realize their identity, to become a force that organizes, motivates and leads the social atmosphere, social spirit, and proves that human dignity is not determined by gender. In this case, the idea of gender equality (creating equal rights and equal opportunities for 573 boys and girls) affects the spiritual growth of both the individual and the society, leads to the understanding of people and changes in social thinking. The idea of gender equality is a constructive idea that motivates the formation of the political consciousness of young people in society, independent thinking, and imbibing the principles of equality from a spiritual and spiritual point of view. There is no doubt that education aimed at ensuring gender equality will help in the formation of socially useful, fair, humane, democratic qualities of youth behavior and outlook. Because education infused with the ideas of gender equality can create gender knowledge in young people, change their outlook and beliefs, and affect their psyche. This is especially possible by studying the psychological features of forming the desire of girls to learn the fields they want with responsibility and determination, and to make sure that they can operate in all spheres of society's development in their minds. This has a positive effect on the formation of a sense of love for the Motherland, confidence in contributing to its prosperity, along with relevant spiritual and moral qualities. Therefore, the consistent use of opportunities for gender education in the educational process plays a major role in the development of young people as well-rounded individuals.

Analysis of literature on the subject The principle of gender equality and consideration of differences should be a priority in the science of pedagogy. The specifics of this prioritization are:

- to distinguish between boys and girls when choosing educational material;
- development of special activities of boys and girls;
- organization of educational activities suitable for a certain gender;
- selection of educational materials that serve to form the specific type of activity of each gender; - formation of pedagogic activities aimed at applying strict, didactically formed gender interpretations in the educational process.

In the process of education, it is important to determine the gender-specific personal qualities of students in creating a stable pedagogical system of providing labor education to boys and girls and guiding them to the profession.

For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following during the educational process:

- organizing educational activities aimed at neutralizing and interpreting the differences between boys and girls;
- educate them in the spirit of showing gender equality;
- ensuring that boys and girls work separately during the educational process;
- organization of educational activities that match the personal interests of boys and girls;
- ensuring activity taking into account the specific educational situation. The quality of education depends on how each of the boys and girls will be, what kind of activities they will occupy.

Analysis and results. In order to ensure pedagogical communication between boys and girls in the educational process, it is necessary to recognize their equal rights. Gender mainstreaming in education is based on mutual support and tolerance between boys and girls, and recognition of the right of each gender to be "different". After gaining independence, the national values and traditions of the Uzbek people began to be restored. Especially these days, the issue of gender equality is gaining importance. This is the ground for promotion of our moral values, unique customs and activities of the Uzbek people, and for each of them to occupy a unique position in the educational process. showed the need to prepare. In such conditions, the main attention of public education workers and teachers should be focused on creating a new cultural communication environment between girls and boys, mutual respect, hard work, and love for each other during the educational process. . It is appropriate to use the historical experiences of the Uzbek people. Understanding gender essentially pedagogically consists in perceiving it as a didactic phenomenon that develops the educational process. Gender, that is, the importance of boys and girls as subjects of the educational process, is related to their equal and different educational activities. Gender, that is, equal and different activities of boys and girls should be pedagogically organized and controlled. The purpose of this is to determine the knowledge, skills, abilities and personal qualities of boys and girls and of assessment . In the study of gender equality and differences among students, the main focus is on understanding their own level of individuality. We interpret gender not as boys and girls, but as subjects of the educational process with equal and different opportunities. Differences between genders in the educational process according to their capabilities are related to their activities in the daily educational process. In this, as participants of cooperation in the educational process, male and female students and teachers perform their numerous and diverse learning and management actions based on gender differences. As we continue to study this logic,

first of all, it is necessary to consider the issue of organizing educational work based on gender equality and differences in the educational process, which is important and not completely developed. Gender is a certain certainty based on the use of socially accepted biological criteria to classify individuals as male or female.

Summary. In conclusion, the important strategic goal of gender policy in our country is aimed at improving the place of women in the family of the nation, their financial situation and social well-being. Such a strategy can be seen in the following: it includes the provision of social guarantees for young, low-income families with many children; that uniform social standards are being developed in the field of health and education; 575 attention is being paid to the problems of eliminating violence in the family, creating legal bases for the protection of women's rights.

References:

1. Chrestomaty of the Basics of Gender Research course: / is short from the Russian language. translation. For higher educational institutions. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2003. - (p. 104, 411 b)
- 2 . Pedagogy: Bolshaya sovremennaya encyclopedia / Sost. Eat. S. Rapasevich - M.: "Sovrem. Slovo", 2005. - (p. 440, 720 b)
- 3 . Matlab Tilavova., Pedagogical and psychological possibilities of considering gender equality and differences in the educational process. Pedagogical skills. Scientific-theoretical and methodical journal. Bukhara., 2021. (pp. 13-17, 178 b)
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ta-lim-tizimida-gender-tengligini-ta-tenglini-masalalari/viewer>
5. <https://fll.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/9095/6381>
6. <file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/571-575.pdf>